

Challenges and Prospects of Public Relations as a Tool for Development Communication in Nigeria

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Abstract

This article interrogates the transformative potential of Public Relations (PR) as a tool for development communication in Nigeria. Grounded in the diffusion of innovations theory, it described PR practitioners as change agents who design strategies to promote adoption of innovations across health, agriculture, education and civic engagement. Thus, participatory PR approaches leverage community networks, opinion leaders and digital platforms to enhance the acceptance and effectiveness of developmental initiatives. Development communication complements these PR efforts by fostering co-created, locally framed interventions that actively include marginalised groups, promoting ownership and sustainable impact. Despite these opportunities, structural and institutional barriers political interference, urban bias, elitist orientations, digital divides, and misinformation limit PR's developmental reach. The study highlights the need to reposition PR toward inclusive, dialogic and ethically grounded practices that integrate both digital and traditional channels; strengthening grassroots engagement, fostering strategic partnerships, leveraging hybrid media, proactively countering misinformation and reinforcing ethical frameworks are critical strategies. When aligned effectively, PR and development communication can synergistically mobilise communities, build trust and contribute meaningfully to Nigeria's sustainable development agenda.

Keywords Public Relations, Development Communication, Participatory Communication, Grassroots Engagement, Digital Media, Sustainable Development

Introduction

Public Relations (PR) serves as a strategic tool for communication, stakeholder engagement and reputation management. PR has evolved from merely promoting organisational image and reputation into a strategic instrument for advancing developmental objectives. It is used to foster dialogue, trust, cooperation and support of people in order to mobilise them for community development projects. In the Nigerian context, the persistent challenges of poverty, poor healthcare services and unemployment

as well as food insecurity heighten the need for PR to emerge as a powerful tool to support development communication in both rural and urban areas (Akintoye, 2025).

Development communication on the other hand is anchored on participatory, problem-solving approaches, inclusive dialogue, grassroots mobilisation and active citizen engagement to enhance development. Historically, development communication gained prominence in the 1960s - 1970s when newly independent nations used media to address underdevelopment (Nnaemeka, 2021). In Nigeria, PR complements efforts of development by providing platforms for public dialogue, designing persuasive campaigns, and shaping opinion toward national development goals. It also supports inclusive governance, strengthens institutions and fosters civic engagement through well-structured communication initiatives such as government-led campaigns and grassroots media interventions (Chile, 2025).

However, PR's role in development communication remains contested. This is because campaigns in health, agriculture, and education are often limited by political interference, urban bias, elitism and weak grassroots engagement (Pate, 2021). Digital media offers opportunities for participatory engagement but is constrained by misinformation, regulatory gaps, and digital divides (Apuke, 2024).

PR and development communication share goals of fostering dialogue, mobilising communities and promoting social change; however, in Nigeria, PR has focused primarily on image-building, while development communication often relies on top-down approaches. The dual limitation undermines their ability to facilitate inclusive development. Pertinently, political interference, weak institutional support, censorship, and limited participatory integration further constrain their impact. Digital opportunities exist but remain underutilised due to inequalities and misinformation, raising questions about PR's readiness to contribute effectively to development outcomes in Nigeria. This study, therefore, interrogates challenges and prospects of Public Relations practice as a tool for development communication in Nigeria.

Public Relations, Development Communication and Participatory Models

Public relations and development communication share a common foundation in strategic messaging, persuasion and dialogue, which are essential for fostering mutual understanding between institutions and communities. Development communication has historically evolved from modernisation and diffusion frameworks, largely top-down information which flows-to participatory and empowerment-oriented models that prioritise local ownership, inclusiveness and grassroots engagement (Nweze & Awoniyi, 2023). As Akintola, Iyinoluwa & Ifeduba (2024) further averred that PR theory has moved beyond publicity and propaganda traditions toward dialogic and stakeholder-centred approaches that emphasise relationship-building and accountability. Within the Nigerian context, however, the developmental potential of PR is constrained by structural challenges, including weak professional standards, insufficient training, political interference, media fragmentation, and inadequate institutional support (Onah, 2025). Despite these limitations, prospects remain significant. Thus, the expansion of digital communication platforms, the growing mobilisation of youth populations, and the increasing application of PR in health campaigns, peacebuilding initiatives and civic engagement demonstrate the capacity of PR to promote trust, inclusive dialogue and collective action in advancing Nigeria's developmental agenda.

Public Relations Practice in Nigeria: Trends and Institutional Context

The practice of PR in Nigeria has evolved significantly with the advertising and adoption of digital platforms by organisations and institutions to project their image and reputations to the global world. Nonetheless, its effectiveness as a tool for development communication remains constrained by structural and professional challenges. PR practice is often politicised and event-driven, prioritising publicity and press releases over participatory engagement (Okoro & Nwafor, 2019). Public sector communication remains predominantly one-way, undermining inclusivity and grassroots mobilisation critical for sustainable development (Oseni, 2024). Furthermore, weak enforcement of professional standards by the Nigerian Institute of Public Relations (NIPR) exacerbates ethical lapses and uneven professionalisation (Nigeria PR Report, 2020).

Despite these limitations, opportunities exist in repositioning PR as the needed tool for advancing development communication. Thus, the rise of social media, youth-led advocacy and community-focused campaigns demonstrates the potential for PR in driving behavioural change, accountability, and inclusive dialogue (Africa PR and Communications Report, 2023). However, strengthening of regulatory enforcement body, investing in capacity building, and integrating PR into public policy procedure could enhance its developmental role. By and large, PR in Nigeria stands at a crossroads: constrained by institutional weaknesses but buoyed by digital transformation and civic participation.

Development Communication in Nigeria: Empirical Evidence and Sectorial Case Studies

Empirical studies on development communication in Nigeria demonstrates that participatory approaches significantly improve outcomes in health, agriculture and education, particularly through community-driven messaging that enhances trust and acceptance and agricultural extension using locally framed and dialogic methods that promote innovation adoption (Basse, 2019). However, a critical challenge lies in the inconsistent adoption of such participatory strategies across sectors and regions. These programmes, according to (Ibuot, Udo & Adeyemi, 2022), persist in relying on donor-driven or top-down designs such as pseudo-participation in water-supply projects which undermine long-term sustainability, local ownership and the integration of indigenous knowledge systems.

According to Gukurume (2018), inadequate infrastructure, low literacy levels, and weak policy frameworks continue to undermine the institutionalisation of participatory practices. These scholars cited the low involvement of communities in most stages of development projects in many Africa countries as case study. This is as recent scholarship of Adetola, Olatunji & Olomjobi (2024), underscores these challenges by proposing a participatory and sustainable communication framework for Nigerian agricultural research institutes, highlighting the necessity of inclusive, multi-stakeholder feedback loops. This reality underscores the value of local communication channels and opinion leaders, embedding such practices into Nigeria's development policies remains a concern.

Public Relations as a Tool for Development Communication: Synergies and Constraints

Public relations remains a double-edged tool in Nigeria's development communication landscape. It offers both synergies and constraints in approaches and application. Strategically, PR employs stakeholder mapping, media relations, and community outreach to mobilise resources, legitimise initiatives, and shape public opinion in support of development programmes (Akintola *et al* 2024). The collaborations between PR professionals and development agencies also allow for culturally grounded campaigns that combine mass and interpersonal channels. (Okoro & Nwafor, 2019) urged that the practice in Nigeria is undermined by politicisation, weak regulatory enforcement, and a heavy reliance on one-way publicity models.

Moreover, the profession's traditional focus on reputation management often conflicts with participatory communication required for grassroots mobilisation (Oseni, 2024). Nonetheless, the expansion of digital platforms, youth activism and community-centred advocacy presents opportunities to reposition PR as a catalyst for inclusive development (Africa PR and Communications Report, 2023).

Digital Media, Misinformation and Governance Challenges

Digital media has transformed PR practice in Nigeria by expanding communication reach and creating interactive spaces for development advocacy. Apuke (2024) notes that social media platforms accelerate health and civic campaigns, enabling rapid mobilisation and agenda-setting. This enhances PR's potential to move beyond event-driven publicity and also contribute to participatory development communication. Nevertheless, significant challenges persist.

The prevalence of misinformation and disinformation erodes public trust, while information overload weakens message clarity and reduces effectiveness. Moreover, the digital divide disproportionately excludes rural populations, limiting PR's inclusivity and relevance of development (Nweze *et al*, 2023). These issues are further compounded by weak governance structures, limited media literacy, and inadequate regulatory enforcement, which undermine ethical practice (Okoro *et al*, 2019). Despite these constraints, prospects remain promising. Hybrid strategies that integrate digital tools with interpersonal communication, coupled with strengthened ethics and media literacy, could reposition PR as a credible instrument for inclusive and sustainable development communication in Nigeria.

Structural and Political Barriers to Effective Practice

Structural and political barriers continue to constrain the effectiveness of PR as a tool for development communication in Nigeria. Thus, political interference and censorship undermine media independence, eroding the credibility of both PR campaigns and development journalism (Oseni, 2024). This reduces opportunities for participatory communication and limited watchdog role of the media in governance.

Similarly, the urban bias of reporting and programme design leaves rural communities underserved, further widen the communication gap in areas where development advocacy is most critical (Okoro *et al*, 2019). In addition, weak institutional support, inadequate funding and overreliance on event-driven publicity have curtailed the sustainability of development-focused campaigns (Nigeria PR Report, 2020). These

systemic weaknesses demonstrate the need for reforms in governance, inclusive media policy, and continuous capacity building for communication practitioners. Without such reforms, PR's transformative potential in advancing inclusive and sustainable development will remain unrealised.

Theoretical Framework

The study is well anchored on the diffusion of innovations theory in public relations and development communication theory. The diffusion of innovations Theory was developed by Everett Rogers in 1962 and redefined in his 2003 edition. The Theory originated in rural sociology to explain how farmers adopted hybrid seeds and fertilizers. Drawing from sociology, communication and marketing, Rogers showed that the spread of innovations follows a patterned process shaped by communication, social systems, and adopter categories. In public relations, the theory positions practitioners as change agents who design communication strategies that speed adoption of new behaviours, services or technologies. PR employs channels such as mass media, social media and interpersonal networks to reach adopter categories, while opinion leaders and early adopters legitimise messages and model desired behaviours.

In Nigeria, digital platforms and stakeholder mapping are become crucial, but success depends on aligning messages with perceived advantages and using trusted local influencers (Nwaobi, 2024). In development communication, diffusion explains how agricultural practices, health behaviours or civic innovations spread across communities. The combination of mass campaigns with interpersonal extension ensures wider uptake, yet adoption is stronger when messages are participatory and locally framed (Spencer, 2023). Structural barriers such as digital divides, urban bias, and misinformation remain challenges. The theory is relevant to this study thus it offers a practical lens for mobilising PR as a development tool in Nigeria by identifying target groups, effective channels, and message attributes while addressing contextual constraints (Adeyemo, 2024).

Methodology

This study adopted a theoretical and qualitative research design by synthesising existing literature, theories and conceptual frameworks to examine how Public Relations can be repositioned as a tool for development communication in Nigeria.

A systematic review of scholarly sources published between 2016 and 2024 was undertaken to ensure relevance to contemporary communication dynamics in Nigeria (Nigeria PR Report, 2020). The review draws on peer-reviewed journals, academic books and institutional reports that address PR practice, participatory communication, digital engagement, and development challenges. This theoretical approach enables a deeper understanding of the synergies and tensions between PR and development communication, offering insights that inform both academic discourse and practical strategies for sustainable development in Nigeria, without reliance on primary field data.

Discussion

The results of this study indicate that Public Relations practice in Nigeria is slowly evolving from a focus on image management to a more development-oriented role; although, this shift remains inconsistent and constrained. Recent scholarship and industry analyses highlight PR's dual function as both a strategic instrument for governance and a potential facilitator of participatory engagement.

Research shows that PR can mobilise communities, influence public perception and create spaces for dialogue among government entities, civil society and citizens. For instance, (Akintola *et al*, 2024) note that Nigerian PR scholarship increasingly positions practitioners as catalysts for change, particularly when campaigns adopt participatory and dialogic methods rather than solely one-way communication. The Nigeria PR Report (2020) also emphasises the growing recognition of PR as a tool for national discussions on health, education, and civic responsibility, beyond mere corporate image and reputation promotion.

Evidence also suggests that development outcomes are enhanced when PR initiatives employ participatory approaches. (Oseni, 2024) found that rural campaigns are more successful when they engage traditional leaders, local media, and interpersonal networks. Likewise, Nweze *et al*, (2023) observed higher effectiveness in agricultural and health programmes when PR and development communication prioritise community dialogue over top-down messaging. This aligns with the diffusion of innovations theory, where opinion leaders and early adopters legitimise messages and facilitate wider adoption.

Additionally, the rise of digital platforms has opened new avenues for PR-driven development communication. Apuke (2024) highlighted that social media initiatives in public health rapidly increased awareness and mobilisation, though misinformation remained a challenge. The Africa PR and Communications Report (2023), further notes that while Nigerian PR practitioners are increasingly using digital tools for civic engagement, unequal internet access leaves rural areas underserved, highlighting the need to combine online and offline channels. Nonetheless, challenges such as political interference, elitist orientations and weak institutional support continue to undermine PR's credibility and inclusivity (Pate, 2021; Oseni, 2024). Event-focused publicity often overshadows sustained developmental campaigns, while urban bias limits outreach to rural populations where needs are greatest. Regulatory gaps and misinformation also complicate digital strategies (Apuke, 2024). These factors illustrate that without reforms including strengthened ethical oversight, professional capacity building and alignment with participatory communication as PR may underperform in driving development.

Overall, the study demonstrates that PR occupies a vital yet contested space in Nigeria's development communication landscape. While participatory PR strategies have shown success in health, agriculture and education, structural and institutional limitations remain. Integrating PR into the country's sustainable development agenda requires shifting from elitist and image-driven approaches toward dialogic, community-focused and ethically guided practices that leverage both digital and traditional communication channels.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that Public Relations can be a powerful tool for development communication in Nigeria by positioning practitioners as change agents who facilitate the adoption of innovations in health, agriculture, education and civic engagement. Participatory strategies, combined with trusted community networks, opinion leaders and digital platforms, enhance programme reach, acceptance and sustainability. Development communication ensures initiatives are co-created with communities, promoting inclusive participation, locally relevant messaging, and engagement of marginalised groups. Overcoming barriers such as misinformation, digital inequities and urban bias requires dialogic, ethically guided PR practices. Embedding genuine participation strengthens trust, ensures equitable access to resources and positions PR as an effective instrument for achieving sustainable socio-economic development. Thus, PR practitioners should prioritise grassroots engagement by prioritising two-way communication models that empower citizens to contribute to decision-making. Using local languages, community radio and indigenous communication systems will ensure inclusivity and build trust in developmental campaigns.

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